

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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The efficient approach to teaching English relies on the traditional methods of foreign language acquisition. Nevertheless, the influence of psychological factors, foreign films, and technology has been significant. Teaching methods employed two decades ago were primarily focused on reproduction. Memorizing vocabulary, reading passages, listening to recordings, and composing letters constituted typical assignments given by instructors. It is likely that due to this approach, many long-time learners can proficiently read and write in English but struggle with speaking fluently.

Contemporary approaches to teaching English have replaced rote methods with interactive ones. Nowadays, acquiring knowledge involves a dynamic exchange between student and teacher. The curriculum is primarily tailored to the age-specific characteristics of the students. For young learners and preschoolers, activities such as games, field trips, videos, competitions, and others are more suitable. Adult students, on the other hand, tend to prefer a more traditional lesson format. Tasks like composing a story, completing exercises, reading texts, and listening activities are also appropriate for this age group. Writing a story helps develop active and passive vocabulary, expand one's lexicon, and improve speaking skills. Completing exercises aids in learning grammatical concepts. Reading texts not only enhances reading abilities, but also immerses students in the culture and traditions of the language being studied. Listening activities improve comprehension of spoken language [1].

Remember that the most successful ways to study English involve active participation. That is why immersing students in an English-speaking environment

is highly recommended. This approach helps them develop the ability to think in English. When learning a new language, the entire process is conducted in English. This is not only true in a bilingual household, but also in a regular classroom. The pedagogue simply needs to conduct the lesson entirely in English and use visual aids. By structuring the lesson in a way that students can understand despite the foreign language, they can effectively learn.

Having a well-trained tutor will enable students to carry out this task even with the youngest students. In the past, parents of preschoolers and young elementary students were hesitant about this approach, but now, witnessing the excitement and progress of their children, they have acknowledged its effectiveness. Ultimately, the most effective way to learn English is one that sparks a desire to learn, as stated by A. Leontyev [2].

As it may be aware, the human brain is most active and efficient in processing and retaining information during the first half of life. Therefore, in the case of English and many other subjects, it is crucial to provide opportunities for learning. In schools and universities, students are taught using various textbooks developed both in Uzbekistan and abroad, but they are primarily based on the communicative approach.

This method of teaching English in primary school focuses on developing children's abilities in reading, writing, listening, and speaking. The materials in these textbooks aim to help students understand authentic texts, situations, and audio dialogues. The lessons are structured around relevant and important topics, such as family, school, and hobbies. Educators often assign tasks for students to work in pairs or groups, encouraging them to use English to communicate with each other and become comfortable with speaking freely.

One of the methods we use is project-based learning. Over the course of several classes, students become familiar with a topic, new vocabulary, grammar rules, and interesting information. To reinforce the material, educators encourage them to create a project, individually, either in pairs, or in groups, and then present and discuss it. Through these activities, children develop their language skills and

discover their creative potential. The project approach not only ensures a thorough understanding of the educational material, but also promotes the intellectual and moral growth of students, fostering independence, kindness towards the teacher and peers, sociability, and a desire to help others. The competition, arrogance, rudeness, and authoritarianism often seen in traditional teaching methods are incompatible with this approach. The project methodology emphasizes a personalized approach to students, recognizing their individual needs, abilities, and aspirations [3].

I am a teacher at learning center “LINDL” situated in Yunusabad district, I have been teaching for two years. I have learned from my own experience that it makes no sense to spend time in explaining grammatical categories, whether it is the concept of time or the order of words in a sentence, no matter how visibly and colorfully it is done. Playing on a specific topic can teach students much faster and without much effort. In the process of language learning for primary school age students, an educational game plays an important role. The more game subjects that the teacher uses in the lessons, the more interesting they are, the more actively and more firmly the material is absorbed.

Thus, each person decides for what method to practice. But it is best to use them in a complex. Specialist will be able to make the right approach to learning and a lesson plan competently. Teacher is simply necessary, as she/he will constantly encourage students to learn interesting tasks and communicate. This guarantees that students will not give up learning the language after 3 days, in fact, without even starting it.

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